

Benefits of Education for the Nation's Next Generation

Anita Candra Dewi^{1*}, Haikal², Muh. Luthfi³, Selvira⁴, Priska Febriona Tonapa⁵,
Khaerul Aksanul Muslimin⁶

Agricultural Technology Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering,
Makassar State University Makassar

Corresponding Author: Anita Candra Dewi anitacandradewi@unm.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Benefits,
Education, Generation,
Nation

Received : 05, August

Revised : 10, September

Accepted: 26, October

©2023 Dewi, Haikal, Luthfi, Selvira,
Tonapa, Muslimin: This is an open-
access article distributed under the
terms of the [Creative Commons
Atribusi 4.0 Internasional](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Education is a learning process, knowledge, or abilities and skills that are seen from each person's habits, education is really needed to support knowledge, training, or research. In UUD number 20 of 2003, the National education system in education also contains educational objectives which are basically a forum or means for developing personality and the potential to increase knowledge. Education functions to form a good self from abilities, skills, ethics and morals to make a better person. Education is a means to equip oneself to face the world of society because the world is not only about knowledge but includes social, ethical and civilized aspects. Of course, education has benefits for those who attend education, because it will have a great influence on both themselves and their environment, which will be examined more clearly in the next discussion.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a process of learning, knowledge, or abilities and skills seen from everyone's habits, education is needed to support knowledge, training, or research. In Constitution number 20 of 2003, it has regulated the national education system in education also contains educational objectives which are basically as a forum or means in developing personality and the potential to increase knowledge.

Education serves to form a good self from abilities, skills, ethics, and morals to make a better person. Education is a means to equip themselves in facing the world of society because the world is not only about knowledge but includes social, ethical, and civil.

Of course, education has benefits for those who follow education, because it will greatly affect both themselves and their environment, it will be more clearly studied in the next discussion.

Education is a learning process about knowledge and skills that can be done anywhere and anytime. Education can be obtained for everyone from childhood to old age. Education is very important for all people who aim to educate and develop their potential. By growing and developing each individual can have creativity, broader knowledge, good personality and being a responsible person.

Education can be done anywhere such as formal education, education carried out in schools or called structured education. In addition, there is also non-formal education, the education is carried out outside formal education for example course institutions (tutoring), training institutions (extracurricular), study groups, and others. There is also informal education, education obtained in the family or the surrounding environment.

The younger generation is the frontline in building the nation and as the next generation of the nation, where the current generation must have broader abilities and knowledge for the future. In addition, education also plays an important role in advancing the country to produce quality human resources. Another reason why education is important is to create the spirit of nationalism. The fewer generations who carry out education, the fewer generations who have the spirit of nationalism.

Nationalism is a sense of belonging to the nation and state, if there is less sense of nationalism it can cause the younger generation who do not care about the nation and country in the future. In addition, to build the character of the younger generation, character education is very important because it teaches us about polite norms, religious norms, and other norms. By following all these norms, the younger generation will have a strong character which is needed to build the future.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

There are so many definitions formulated by experts in looking at education. Before looking at the understanding of education as a whole, it's good to first look at some terms that often appear and are related to education itself. The terms are pedagogical and pedagogical. According to Ngalm Purwanto, pedagogic means education, while pedagogic means education.

As for the broader definition of education in Indonesian large dictionary, education is the process of changing one's attitude and behavior or groups of people in an effort to mature humans through teaching and training efforts.

From the definition of the definition of education above, it can be concluded that education is a process of maturing humans or individuals who are written in changes in behavior (personality) and cognitive (intelligence) and self-awareness in order to become a whole person. The Education experts define education as follows.

1. W.J.S. Poerwadarminta (1985: 702) explains linguists, as a noun, education means the process of changing one's attitude and behavior to mature humans through teaching and training efforts.
2. Rechey in his book, the term education deals with the broad function of maintaining and improving people's lives, especially to introduce new citizens (younger generation) to the introduction of their obligations and responsibilities in the community. Thus, the educational process is an important social activity whose function is to transform the state of a society into a social state so closely that education may undergo a process of specialization and institutionalization according to the needs of complex and modern society. However, the overall education process cannot be separated from the informal education process that takes place outside the school.
3. The term education, in English education, comes from the word educate, which is nurturing, educating. In the Dictionary of Education, education is a collection of all processes that allow a person to develop abilities, attitudes, and behaviors that are of positive value in society. The term education is also a sausage process when a person is faced with the influence of a selected and controlled environment (especially the social environment) so that they can have optimal social skills and individual development.
4. Education is an effort made deliberately and systematically to motivate, foster, help, and guide a person to develop all his potential so that he achieves better self-quality. The essence of education is the effort to mature the whole person (born and inward), both by himself and others, in the sense of guidance so that students have the freedom to think, feel, speak, and act and are confident with a sense of responsibility in every daily action and behavior.

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative research is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. It can be used to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships, and generalize results to wider populations. Quantitative research is the opposite of qualitative research, which involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data (e.g., text, video, or audio). Quantitative research is widely used in the natural and social sciences: biology, chemistry, psychology, economics, sociology, marketing, etc.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

From the understanding of education, it can understand that education has several theoretical meanings and practical meanings, which are as follows:

1. Education means teaching everything that is beneficial to human life, both to physical activity, mind and to sharpness and meekness of conscience.
2. Education can be based on community culture, religious values, and the vision and mission of educational institutions.
3. Education can work, both formally and informally.

According to Suyitno, if carried out with reference to a solid foundation, education can be carried out steadily, clearly with its purpose, relevant to the content of the curriculum, as well as effective and efficient methods or ways of implementation. Therefore, before carrying out education, educators must strengthen their educational foundation. Considering that the essence of education is humanization, which is an effort to humanize humans, educators must understand human nature as one of the foundations.

In the education system, there is a transformation process, which is essentially a process of converting raw inputs (students) into 5 outputs (educated humans according to predetermined educational goals). Ideally, all components of education carry out their respective functions and interact with each other leading to the achievement of educational goals. The output is intended for the community or other systems in the suprasystem (society).

According to M.J. Langeveld (1980), education or educating is an adult effort made intentionally to help children or immature people in an environment. Because education is sought intentionally, educators choose certain educational content and use certain educational tools as well.

The purpose of education in Indonesia is written in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia (UURI) Number 20 Tahun 2003 concerning the Education System along with government regulations related to education in general. In the government regulation of the Republic of Indonesia (PPRI) NoMOR 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards Article 26 Paragraph 1 it is stated that basic education aims to lay the foundation of Intelligence, Knowledge, Personality, noble Akhalak, Skills for independent living, and Follow further education.

The purpose of education can be divided into two, namely general goals and specific objectives as follows:

1. General Purpose of Education

Education aims to produce students who believe. The manifestation of that goal is the morals of students which refers to the curriculum applied in education carried out in various institutions, both formal and non-formal educational institutions.

Goals are goals to be achieved as well as guidelines that memberi arah aktivitas yang Done. Al-Abrasyi lays out the purpose of education in more detail into five types, namely:

1. Forming noble morals, because one of the most basic goals of education is the formation of morals and purity of soul;
2. Preparing students to be happy in the world and hereafter

3. Preparation for a living, or more famously now with vocational and professional goals
4. Fostering the scientific spirit of students and satisfying their curiosity;
5. Preparing students to become reliable professionals and technicians, and have the skills to work in society

The purpose of education can be seen from various aspects. In terms of gradation, there is an ultimate goal and a temporary goal. Judging by its nature, there are general and special purposes. In terms of its implementation and the purpose of formal, informal and non-formal education. In formal education there are national, institutional, curricular (field of study), and instructional goals. Judging by the output, there are individual goals and social goals. In the field of study (curriculum), educational goals are divided into religious goals, intellectual goals, cultural goals, material goals, and psychic goals (Afifuddin, 2004: 13).

In substance, the general goal of ending the educational process, that is, universally accepted normative maturity that has its own value. The characteristics of maturity which are the general objectives of education, among others:

1. Maturity is static and closed because it has attained an integrated status in individual, social and moral development;
2. Responsible for oneself so as to be able to align individual interests with social interests;
1. Individuals as individuals are aware of their stability so that they are able to appreciate differences of opinion with others and are consistent in prioritizing the resolution of social conflicts in ways nonviolent peace including conflicts involving his person;
1. Willing to be tested (judged) in social life on the basis of His ability to explore and live the "choice of moral action" in accordance with human dignity:
2. Also constructively create the well-being of others without neglecting one's own interests and well-being;
3. Have the ability to process norms that come from outside and from society before being made into norms that mean personal autonomy (Waini Rasyidin, 2007: 45).

1. Special Purpose of Education

According to the National Education System Law No. 20 of 2003, "National education functions to develop the ability and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to educate the nation's life, aims to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic citizens and responsibilities.

Based on the understanding of the objectives of national education, as stated in UUSPN No. 20 of 2003 in relation to making schools as centers of culture, education carried out is meaningful as a process of developing value

capabilities and attitudes that are relevant to the demands of the development of the Indonesian nation state. Both Law No. 2 of 1989 and Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, contain provisions for study materials and compulsory lessons learned from elementary to secondary school.

The specific objectives of education can also refer to the competency standards of its graduates, namely:

1. Behave in accordance with religious teachings in accordance with adolescent development.
 2. Develop yourself optimally by utilizing your strengths and improving your shortcomings.
 3. Show confidence and take responsibility for his behavior, deeds, and work.
 4. Participate in the enforcement of social rules.
 5. Respect the diversity of religions, nations, tribes, races, and socio-economic groups in the global scope.
 6. Build and apply information and knowledge logically, critically, creatively, and innovatively.
-
1. Demonstrate the ability to think logically, critically, creatively, and innovatively in decision making.
 2. Demonstrate the ability to develop a culture of learning for self-empowerment.
 3. Show a competitive and protective attitude to get the best results.
 4. Demonstrate the ability to analyze and solve complex problems.
 5. Demonstrate the ability to analyze natural and social symptoms.
 6. Make productive and responsible use of the environment.
 7. Participate in the life of society, nation, and state democratically within the forum of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia
 8. Express yourself through artistic and cultural activities.
 9. Appreciating art and culture.
 10. Produce creative work, both individually and in groups
 11. Maintain personal health and safety, physical fitness, and environmental hygiene.
 12. Communicate orally and in writing effectively and courteously.
 13. Understand the rights and obligations of self and others in association in society.
 14. Respect differences of opinion and empathize with others.
 15. Demonstrate systematic and aesthetically sound reading and scriptwriting skills.
 16. Demonstrate listening, reading, and writing and speaking skills in Indonesian and English.
 17. Mastering the knowledge necessary to attend higher education.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Education is the process of maturing humans or individuals who are written in changes in behavior (personality) and cognitive (intelligence) and self-awareness in order to become a whole person. According to one expert,

Rechey in his book, the term education is concerned with the broad function of maintaining and improving people's lives, especially to introduce new citizens (younger generation) to the introduction of their obligations and responsibilities in the community. Thus, the educational process is an important social activity whose function is to transform the state of a society into a social state so closely that education may undergo a process of specialization and institutionalization according to the needs of complex and modern society. However, the overall education process cannot be separated from the informal education process that takes place outside the school.

In education there are several benefits of having dan instrumental, a simple example is the basic ability to read and write (literacy) and numerical counting that provides benefits sangat luas bagi community. As a place to deepen a Science, education can be useful for someone who wants to deepen a discipline.

FURTHER STUDY

This study is aim to support the Emergence of IT sector in India and Gujarat. Hopefully it will useful for the reader and if there another researcher used this research for the next research, be objective.

REFERENCE

Hendasjah, Hidajat. 2009. Is It Worth Your Child's Education Costs? A simple way to reason the allocation of financing in the Field of Education. Jakarta: Gramedia.

Ihsan, Fuad. 2005. Fundamentals of education. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta

Sugiyono. (2017). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.

Sugiyono. (2019). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D. Bandung: Alfabeta.

Suyatno. (2009). Menjelajah Pembelajaran Inovatif, Sidoarjo: Masmmedia Buana Pustaka.

Tatang. 2012. Science of Islamic Education. Bandung : Pustaka Setia.